

6th E-NEWSLETTER | July 2024

In our third issue for 2024, we are thrilled to share the news on the Open Days organised by RECONMATIC and the advancements in our research efforts.

What is clear, as we approach the end of the second year of the project is that our clustering activities and synergies flourish. Learn more about the results of our collaborations with other initiatives and projects, in research, technical tasks and dissemination of our results.

Read below all you need to know about our activities and keep an eye on what's coming in the months ahead.

Happy reading!

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NEWS

Meet RECONMATIC in China: Discussing worldwide strategies

As the collaboration of the EU, the UK and the Chinese partners for the RECONMATIC project advances, we are thrilled to announce our 3rd Open Day Event in Shaoxing, China, on August 21st, 2024. The event will bring together key stakeholders from Europe and China to discuss international collaboration for construction and demolition waste management and pave the way for more innovative and effective sustainability strategies worldwide.

Circular economy at the core of the 2nd RECONMATIC Open Day in Manchester

A banner for an Open Day event in Manchester, UK. The left side features the Reconmatic logo and the event title 'Open Day in Manchester, UK' in green and white text. Below the title, the date 'May 7, 2024' is listed, along with the times '09.00 - 17.00'. The right side of the banner shows a modern building at night with blue and white lights, identified as 'MediaCity campus - University of Salford'. A large black play button icon is centered over the banner. At the bottom, there are logos for 'Funded by the European Union', 'UK Research and Innovation', and 'Supported by ciria' and 'ZERO WASTE SOLUTIONS'.

The RECONMATIC partners proudly organised a successful Open Day event in Manchester on May 7th, 2024. The event featured engaging workshops and

presentations on developed technologies for sustainability and circularity in the construction sector. Find out more on our dedicated webpage!

[Learn more](#)

Related Article

[Students' workshop:](#)
[Playing cards for Innovation & Circular Economy.](#)

China's Role in Global Sustainability: RECONMATIC in World Circular Economy Forum

The "World Circular Economy Forum (WCEF)", on April 15-18, 2024, in Brussels, Belgium was a great opportunity for RECONMATIC's Chinese partner, the China Association of Circular Economy (CACE) to attend, gain useful insights into the circular

economy and present the perspective of the RECONMATIC project for China and the collaboration potential worldwide.

[Learn more](#)

BLOG

Sustainability and circularity indicators by RECONMATIC

How is circularity in construction defined? How can we measure circularity and sustainability in construction or infrastructure works? Learn more about the methodological steps followed by the experts in this thorough article.

[Learn more](#)

PUBLICATIONS

RECONMATIC presents publications on “Point Cloud to BIM Using Python Codes” & “End of Life Strategies and Sustainable Demolition Technologies for Buildings”

RECONMATIC's new paper on automated creation of digital model for end-of-service life buildings

New scientific paper: “Boosting confidence in circular construction and demolition waste management: a DPSIR framework analysis”

Social Media Campaign: 30 must-read publications on Digital and Circular construction

CLUSTER NEWS & SYNERGIES

The masterminds behind the “buildingSMART Data Dictionary”

Our UK partner, Bimbox, reveals how they used a data dictionary to build an information exchange for construction waste, called WASTEie, in collaboration with Dr. Arghavan Akbarieh from Eindhoven University of Technology. Let the team guide you through the steps to use this data dictionary!

[Learn more](#)

Circular Construction Cluster: Paving the way in the European construction sector

[Joint study on Stakeholders' perception of circular economy in construction presented at CESARE'24 Conference](#)

[Stakeholders' Training on Circularity strategies and best practices for new and existing buildings](#)

[RECONMATIC Guidance Tool for Circularity presented in the 1st CircularB COST Action Webinar](#)

[Setting KPIs for Assessing Circularity and Sustainability in Construction: Open Call to stakeholders](#)

Survey

[To Circular Economy Stakeholders: 10 minutes to participate in the International Survey for barriers to implementing Circular Economy practices in the built environment](#)

[Read the CircularB Newsletter for more Activities on Circular Construction](#)

TECH4EUConstruction Cluster

[How can we realise a digitally controlled circular construction? Reincarnate's project research collection \(article on BUILD UP\)](#)

[Human-centric innovation and skills for safety in construction, by the Beeyonders Project \(article on BUILD UP\)](#)

EVENTS

RECONMATIC in SPARC 2024, Brisbane

Smart Cities at the URBIS Conference 2024

RECONMATIC at ArchiDays 2024 conference

Take aways from the Digital Construction Week 2024'

RECONMATIC solutions presented in RECYCLING 2024

Paving the way in European research and innovation in CZEDER 2024

Upcoming Activities

During this summer the RECONMATIC partners are intensively preparing for the **Open Day in China** on the 21st of August and the project's annual meeting in Thessaloniki Greece, on the 16-17 of September. We are also working on the validation workshop of the RECONMATIC Guidance and Assessment tool for Circularity and Sustainability in Construction, that will take place at the end of September.

Contact us if you are interested in joining us in the above meetings and workshop!

Save the date and stay tuned via the project's social media channels on LinkedIn (**@RECONMATIC**) and X (Twitter) (**@reconmatic**) to never miss updates on our activities!

Subscribe to our website to receive directly in your inbox updates about the project's activities and progress.

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